

**SUBJECT-VERB AGREEMENT ERRORS FOUND IN THE
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Subject-Verb Agreement Errors Found in the Students' Reflective Comments on Dr. Craig Refugio's YouTube Channel: An Action Research

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Abstract

The study investigated the Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) errors committed by third-year students of Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) found in the students' reflective comments on Dr. Craig Refugio's YouTube Channel. Screenshots of the Ed303 (Methods of Research) sections D and F comments were taken, and content analysis was done to identify the number of SVA errors committed by the students in their written outputs. Additionally, an interview with the participants took place to determine the reasons for their errors. The study revealed that most third-year students in ED303 Sections D and F classes had committed SVA errors. A significant percentage of them were females and Filipino majors who came from public high schools. These students committed SVA errors because of their lack of foundational knowledge, confusion about the SVA rules, absence of comprehensive knowledge of SVA, failure to review and proofread the written outputs because of time constraints, and their first language preference over the second language. Hence, an awareness program of SVA-related activities, collaboration with the university English club, and free access to Grammarly software and other grammar checker tools are recommended to help resolve the problem.

Keywords: *Subject-verb agreement (SVA) rules, SVA errors, content analysis, Grammarly software, awareness program*

INTRODUCTION

This action research was based on Craig Mertler's *two organizational schemes for the step-by-step process of Action Research*. Mills (as cited in Mertler, 2017) defined action research as any systematic investigation carried out by educators to learn more about how their schools run, how they teach, and how their students learn. It is a process that enables teachers in a classroom context to examine their classrooms, understand them better, and enhance their effectiveness or quality (Mertler, 2020a). It is undoubtedly the best method for dealing with contextualized organizational issues and responding to relevant questions (Mertler, 2020b). As illustrated in Figure 1 below, Mertler's framework follows a cyclical process comprising four stages: planning, acting, developing, and reflecting. In the planning

Figure 1. Craig Mertler's (2017) two organizational schemes for the step-by-step process

stage, practitioners identify a topic, gather information through literature reviews or consultations, and formulate research questions to guide the study. The acting stage involves collecting and analyzing data using methods best suited to the study's nature, such as qualitative, quantitative, or mixed approaches. During the developing stage, researchers create actionable plans based on findings to address current issues and prepare for future cycles, acknowledging that solutions often require multiple iterations. Finally, the reflecting stage allows for critically evaluating the research process and outcomes, providing insights that inform subsequent cycles and ensure continuous improvement.

Stage 1: Planning Stage

Step 1: Identifying and limiting the topic

English is currently the world's lingua franca, being the dominant language used by people across races. In the Philippines, it is considered the second official language. Unfortunately, due to the significant differences in the native language's grammar form and structure, most Filipinos struggle with writing error-free sentences despite being dubbed as one of the world's largest English users. College professors point out that some of the troublesome grammatical "errors" in students' writing are the SVA rules (Behrens, 2010). The standard SVA suggests that singular subjects must go with singular verbs, while plural subjects go with plural verbs (Iwan Kurniawan, 2016). Learning about the SVA will ensure that written outputs will be precise, understandable, and stylistically appropriate (Indiana University of Pennsylvania, n.d.). It is essential for achieving grammar mastery and, ultimately, mastery of all other aspects of the English language (Cabaltica & Osabel, 2021). Based on the previous and current English secondary curriculum college students went through before ascending to the tertiary level, SVA is already included in the two productive macro-skills of English, writing and speaking. Following the designs of the English curriculum, students should have been able to master the basics of the SVA rules. However, Senobio (2015) pointed out that despite using the language from elementary to middle school, many students still exhibit poor writing abilities. Their mediocrity in grammar is one of the things that causes this problem. This fact can be further shown through the NORSU Main Campus I students' (from the Ed 303 sections D and F classes, Academic Year 2022-2023) reflective comments on two of the YouTube instructional videos of Dr. Craig N. Refugio, their Ed 303 professor.

Step 2: Gathering information

Some of the Ed 303 sections D and F students' writing abilities do not meet the expected grammatical competence targeted by the English secondary curriculum. The most common non-standard (i.e., errors) SVA rules committed by the students on the two YouTube videos, "Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs" and "Qualitative Research Designs," are the following:

Case no. 1: *Researcher writes* memos during data collection. (The errors are *italicized*.)

additional data collection. Researcher write memos during data collection. In my far understanding in collecting the data it should be in the form of having all the idea in putting to the study. For example when conducting a

Case no. 2: This video *helps* me to know...

study. This video help me to know and have a clear understanding again about what was all case study up until narrative inquiry all about.

Case no. 3: Internal validity *also points out* the study's assurance.

design. Also, the internal validity point out the assurance of the study.

Case no. 4: ... the experimental studies test for cause-and-effect relationships...

Post Facto Designs, I have learned a much clearer distinction between these terms, where the experimental studies is used to test for cause-and-effect relationships; many

Case no. 5: A researcher *selects* individuals with unique or deviant characteristics...

other slide in which he also highlight that case study the researchers also may engage in extreme cases sampling. A researcher select individuals who have unique or deviant characteristics within a case, then focuses

The corrections are *italicized*:

- **Case no. 1:** Researchers *write* memos during data collection.
- **Case no. 2:** This video *helps* me to know...

- **Case no. 3:** Internal validity *also points out* the study's assurance.
- **Case no. 4:** ... the experimental studies test for cause-and-effect relationships...
- **Case no. 5:** A researcher *selects* individuals who have unique or deviant characteristics...

Step 3: Reviewing related literature

Relevant studies have highlighted students' persistent challenges with Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) rules and proposed various interventions to address these issues. Cabaltica and Osabel (2021) in Zambales identified common SVA errors, such as confusion over percentage-related verbs, incorrect usage of expressions like "the number" versus "a number," and errors involving nouns derived from foreign languages. Their findings revealed a correlation between students' grammar skills in SVA and their previous academic performance, leading to the development of a remedial teaching action plan. This study underscores the need to address similar issues among select NORSU students while examining related variables such as sex, majorship, and previous schooling.

Technological approaches have also proven effective. Miranda et al. (2021) developed a mobile application with interactive features to teach SVA rules. Results demonstrated the app's potential to enhance students' grammar skills while engaging them through a fun and immersive learning experience. This suggests integrating technology into instruction can increase students' interest and proficiency in SVA.

In the international context, cooperative learning has emerged as another effective strategy. In Malaysia, Txin and Yunus (2021) demonstrated that cooperative learning fosters individual accountability and collaborative engagement, significantly improving students' mastery of SVA rules. Such approaches provide a structured environment where students enhance their grammatical skills and interpersonal connections.

Additionally, studies by Alahmadi (2019) and Sufian and Harun (2018) revealed frequent SVA errors among tertiary students, particularly with singular and plural subjects and sentences with separated subjects and verbs. Their recommendations—from teacher-student conferences to peer tutoring and inductive grammar lessons—offer practical strategies to address these challenges effectively.

These findings provide a robust foundation for this action research, guiding the development of remedial and innovative strategies. By combining technological interventions, cooperative learning, and targeted pedagogical methods, this study aims to tackle persistent SVA difficulties and support students in mastering this fundamental aspect of grammar.

METHODOLOGY

Step 4: Develop a research plan

This study was conducted in NORSU Main Campus I, situated at the Capitol Area, Kagawasan Avenue, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental. This university is the only state university in the province of Negros Oriental, Philippines, and it has seven (7) satellite campuses. This action research was carried out from December 12-28, 2022.

The research classes focused on by the researchers were the Ed 303 sections D and F students of NORSU Main Campus 1, Academic Year 2022-2023, with a total population of thirty (30) and twenty-eight (28), respectively. The researchers then selected two videos

from Dr. Craig N. Refugio's YouTube Channel, entitled (1) "*Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*" and (2) "*Qualitative Research Designs*," where the reflections of Ed303 students are found and captured through a screenshot. Some of the 58 target participants did not comment on the two selected videos. Nonetheless, content analysis was carried out pertinent to the identification/discrimination of the SVA errors to classify those comments found to have errors and those with none.

The researchers analyzed the data using MegaStat and Microsoft Excel and interpreted the findings accordingly to reveal which group of students in the class committed significantly more frequent SVA errors. To develop a more informed and wholesome intervention, the researchers interviewed every student in Sections D and F who commented on the two videos relative to their perceived reasons why SVA errors were still committed. With a total of 24 responses, the researchers applied MegaStat analysis to interpret the primary reasons why such errors existed.

With SVA as the target grammar construction, this study aimed to investigate the SVA errors found in the reflective comments of the Ed 303 (Methods of Research) sections D and F students of Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) Main Campus I in the Academic Year 2022-2023 with an end view of developing a course of action plan. Specifically, it sought to find answers to the following questions:

1. How many comments are found in the two videos selected in Ed303 course with and without SVA error(s) from:
 - i. Section D; and
 - ii. Section F?
2. What is the frequency distribution of Section D students of the Ed303 course who committed SVA errors in each of the two videos in terms of:
 - i. sex;
 - ii. majorship; and
 - iii. Type of previous school graduated from (either public or private school)?
3. What is the frequency distribution of Section F students of the Ed303 course who committed SVA errors in each of the two videos in terms of:
 - i. sex; and
 - ii. type of previous school graduated from (either public or private school)?
4. What are the reasons why students commit these SVA errors?
5. What course of action can be taken based on the findings?

RESULTS

Stage 2: Acting Stage

Step 5: Collecting data

The following data reveals the cases and analyses of the SVA errors committed by Sections D and F students in the comment section of the two select videos in Dr. Craig N. Refugio's YouTube channel, entitled (1) *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs* and (2) *Qualitative Research Designs*.

Video 1: Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs

Section D (T-Th 10:00-11:30 AM)

In Video 1, 9 out of the 21 comments from Section D commit SVA errors. The comments are as follows:

Case #1

selected individuals. The video discussion give me so much information that enables me to understand further what experimental research design is. I learn a lot especially that

Correction: “**gives**”

The subject "video discussion" is singular; hence, the verb must also be singular. Since the subject is singular, this can be corrected by writing "gives."

Case #2

acknowledge it, and report it. After all the videos that is shown Dr. Craig Refugio presented the copyright that where did he get all the information's that he has shared to us.

Correction: “**are**”

The subject “videos” is plural. Hence, the verb also needs to be in plural form. As is evident in the sentence, the verb should be written as "are" as it can be seen how it should coincide with the subject in the sentence, which is in plural form.

Case #3

With these three experimental design, I only know and heard about quasi-experimental design, so the other two is new to me.

Correction: “**are**”

The subject "two" is plural. Hence, the verb also needs to be in plural form. This sentence can be corrected by replacing the verb with "are." The word "two" is automatically seen as a plural form of subject, so the verb must also be plural.

Case #4

design. Also, the internal validity point out the assurance of the study.

Correction: “**points**”

The subject “internal validity” is singular, so the verb also needs to be in singular form. The word "point" must be changed to "points," as it is appropriate to change the verb from a plural form to a singular form.

Case #5

researches. And in the video what I noticed is that the experimental designs is related or focused on identifying the cause and effect relationship or the relationship of variables and in the ex post facto it is focused on the independent and dependent variables.

Correction: “**are**”

The subject “experimental designs” is plural, so the verb also needs to be in plural form. The word "is" must be changed to its plural form, which is "are," because it needs to correspond to its subject, as the number one rule in SVA in constructing sentences.

Case #6

But even experimental designs is used to test the cause and effect relationship of variables. Through this video also I'm able to

Correction: “**are**”

The subject “experimental designs” is plural; hence, the verb must also be plural. From how the sentence is constructed, one can infer that it is grammatically incorrect. But, focusing on the SVA issue that the sentence possesses, the word "is" must be changed to "are" as the subject used in the sentence is plural.

Case #7

by Dr. Craig Refugio. Based in the video, experimental studies, is where the researcher have to controls all influential elements except those whose probable impacts are the topic of investigation. This aid us future

Correction: “**are**”

The subject “experimental studies” is plural, so the verb also needs to be plural. It is evident that the verb "is" must be changed into "are" since the subject is plural, so the verb must also be plural.

Case #8

happened already. It is because there are other issues that is impossible to use the experimental designs. For example, the effect

Correction: “**are**”

The subject “issues” is plural. Hence, the verb also needs to be in plural form. With the subject in the sentence being the word "issues," the verb it has must also be in plural form; the verb must be written as "are" and not "is."

Case #9

can't control for all confounding variables. I have learned again in the pre-recorded video that a confounding variables **is** those factors that might account for differences that are not attributable to the intervention of being studied. In an Ex Post Favto Design,

Correction: “**are**”

The subject “confounding variables” is plural, so the verb also needs to be in plural form. The verb must be changed to "are," as the word "confounding variables" is plural. Both the subject and the verb must accurately correspond to each other.

Section F (T-Th 2:30-4:00 PM)

In Video 1, 4 out of the 10 comments from Section F commit SVA errors. The comments are as follows:

Case #1

Post Facto Designs, I have learned a much clearer distinction between these terms, where the experimental studies **is** used to test for cause-and-effect relationships; many

Correction: “**are**”

The subject “experimental studies” is plural, hence the verb also needs to be in plural form. So, it should be written as “are” as the subject indicates the plural form in the sentence.

Case #2

design and the ex post facto design. This video **help** us as a researcher in providing information that we may use to create our own research. I also learned that there are

Correction: “**helps**”

The subject “video” is singular; hence, the verb also needs to be in singular form. In this sentence, the verb should be written as "helps" since the subject referred to is singular, and one needs to add the letter "s" in a verb.

Case #3

After watching this video, I have learned new concept which are new and it is about the experimental, quasi-experimental, and ex post facto designs. As mentioned by

Correction: “**is**”

The subject “concept” is singular; hence, the verb also needs to be in singular form. The verb in the sentence should be written as "is" since it is evident that the subject the verb is referring to is in a singular form.

Case #4

designs. In experimental studies, I also find out that it is used to test for the cause-and-effect relationships where the researcher will control influential factors except those whose possible effects are the focus of the investigation.

Correction: “**These are**”

The subject “experimental studies” is plural, so the verb also needs to be in plural form. The verb used in the sentence may be written as "these are" since the subject is plural, and it would be awkward to write the plural form of the verb together with the word "it." So, using "these" and the word "are" would be a great alternative to correct the SVA issue in the sentence.

Video 2: Qualitative Research Designs

Section D (T-Th 10:00-11:30 AM)

In Video 2, 5 out of the 21 comments from Section D commit SVA errors. The comments are as follows:

Case #1

production and the like. In overall i got her different information and i learn new concepts with a video discussion that help me understand well on what is qualitative research methods all about. It helps me

Correction: **“helps”**

The subject "video discussion" is singular; hence, the verb must also be singular. It should be "helps" and not "help," as the general rule of SVA states that singular subjects must take singular verbs, while plural subjects must take plural verbs.

Case #2

validity. And then, strategies for enhancing credibility and reliability was also discussed such as identifying biases, collecting multiple forms of data, separation of observation and interpretations, and many more. These

Correction: **“were”**

The subject "credibility and reliability" is a form of a compound subject. Compound subjects are two terms conjoined by a conjunction, considered plural. So, the verb "was" must agree with the words "credibility and reliability" since, apart from the idea that it can be identified in the plural form, the words are also used from the past, which makes it an example of past tense.

Case #3

identification and evaluation. These advantages is needed in Qualitative Research Methods as it is based on observational that

Correction: **“are”**

The word “advantages” is considered to be in a plural form. So, the verb “is” must agree with the word "advantages." So, the verb must also be plural when the subject is plural.

Case #4

memos. Data collection follows an emerging design. Analysis of early data influences additional data collection. Researcher write memos during data collection. In my far

Correction: **“writes”**

The subject “researcher” is singular, so the verb should also be singular. It should be “writes” and not “write”.

Case #5

continue go evolve over the course of the study. This video help me to know and have a clear understanding again about what was all case study up until narrative inquiry all about.

Correction: “**helps**”

The subject "this video" is singular, so the verb should also be singular. It should be "helps" and not "help".

Section F (T-Th 2:30-4:00 PM)

In Video 2, 5 out of the nine comments from Section F commit SVA errors. They are as follows:

Case #1

On the other hand, narrative inquiry refers to studies that aims on studying complex, multifaceted phenomena. It tend to focus on the recollections and stories of individuals

Correction: “**aim**”

The subject "studies" is plural, so the verb should also be plural. It should be "aim" and not "aims."

Case #2

Moreover, if there is validity and reliability in quantitative research design, there is also credibility and transferability in qualitative research designs. Identifying bias, collecting multiple forms of data, observations

Correction: “**are**”

The phrase "credibility and transferability" is plural, so we use "are" rather than "is." We use "is" for the singular form and "are" for the plural form. It should be noted that the subject of the verb is not "there" but "validity and reliability," which is an example of a compound subject.

Case #3

identification, verification, exploration and evaluation. The video help me to know and have a clear understanding about the case study and the narrative inquiry all about. The uses of case study is to investigate on how individual changes over time, while the

Correction: “**helps**”

The subject "the video" is singular, so the verb should also be singular. It should be "helps" and not "help."

Case #4

This video, titled "Qualitative Research Designs," is has taught me about something like a number of research methods that can be classified as qualitative in addition to the quantitative research designs, which are

Correction: “**has**”

The word "have" is ungrammatical. It should be "has" and not "is has" because the verb has to agree with the singular subject, "this video."

Case #5

the respondents. I have also learned that the validity and reliability is equivalent in terms of quantitative research. Quantitative researcher judge assessment strategies as reliable.

Correction: “**are**”

It must be "are" and not "is" because the words "validity and reliability" are plural since they are compound subjects.

Step 6: Analyzing data

This section details the analysis of the data collected and reports findings in relation to the specific research questions posed in this study.

1. **How many comments are found in the two videos selected in Ed303 course with and without SVA error(s) from:**
 - i. **Section D; and**
 - ii. **Section F?**

Table 1.1 Section D Comments on Two Videos Selected

Two Videos Selected	SECTION D (T-Th 10:00-11:30 AM)		
	Number of Comments WITH SVA Errors	Number of Comments WITHOUT SVA Errors	Total
Video 1 <i>(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>	9	12	21
Video 2 <i>(Qualitative Research Designs)</i>	5	16	21

Of the 28-student population of Section D (T-Th 10:00-11:30 AM), 21 students commented on the two selected videos from Dr. Craig Refugio's YouTube channel. In the first video on *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, 9 of these 21 comments are found to have SVA errors, while 12 comments have none. In the second video on *Qualitative Research Designs*, five comments were found to have SVA errors, while 16 comments had none.

The presence of SVA errors, particularly in reflective writing, suggests a need for students to develop a stronger understanding of grammatical structures. This finding aligns with Kampookaew (2020), who noted that grammatical errors, including subject-verb agreement issues, are prevalent among EFL learners due to inadequate mastery of English tenses and sentence construction. Reflective tasks, which often require students to focus on the meaning and flow of their ideas, may unintentionally deprioritize grammatical accuracy. Similarly, Wahyuni (2019) highlighted that subject-verb agreement errors commonly occur among senior high school and undergraduate students due to challenges in distinguishing singular and plural subjects, compounded by a lack of proofreading practices. The disparity in errors between the two videos in this study may indicate variations in cognitive load and familiarity with the topics, as students might struggle more with grammar when engaging with complex or unfamiliar concepts.

Additionally, Yousefi and Mahmoodi (2022) emphasized that students tend to focus on content rather than grammar when expressing ideas, which is particularly true in reflective or narrative assignments where the emphasis is placed on meaning over form. These studies align with the current findings, suggesting that instructional strategies emphasizing grammar in context can help students improve their writing accuracy. The variance in errors between the two videos may also reflect topic familiarity and cognitive load, as suggested by Amiri and Puteh (2017), who argued that complex or unfamiliar content can lead to lapses in grammatical precision as students focus on comprehending the material. Given this, integrating targeted grammar instruction alongside content delivery may help mitigate such errors, particularly in reflective activities.

Table 1.1.A. Frequency Distribution of Section D Comments on Video 1

<i>Video 1(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
With SVA Errors	9	42.9
Without SVA Errors	12	57.1
	21	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table is generated, showing the frequency distribution of Section D comments in Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, based

on those with SVA errors and those with none. 42.9% of the 21 comments commit SVA errors, while the other 57.1% have no errors. This reveals that over 40% of the comments coming from Section D in Video 1 commit SVA errors.

Table 1.1.B Frequency Distribution of Section D Comments on Video 2

<i>Video 2 (Qualitative Research Designs)</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
With SVA Errors	5	23.8
Without SVA Errors	16	76.2
	21	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table is generated, showing the frequency distribution of Section D comments in Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*, based on those with SVA errors and those with none. 23.8% of the 21 comments commit SVA errors, while 76.2% have no errors. This reveals that at least 20% of the comments coming from Section D in Video 2 commit SVA errors.

Table 1.2 Section F Comments on Two Videos Selected

Two Videos Selected	SECTION D (T-Th 10:00-11:30 AM)		
	Number of Comments WITH SVA Errors	Number of Comments WITHOUT SVA Errors	Total
Video 1 <i>(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>	4	6	10
Video 2 <i>(Qualitative Research Designs)</i>	5	4	9

Out of the 30-student population of Section F (T-Th 2:30-4:00 PM), 10 students commented on Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, 4 of which have SVA errors, while 6 have none. On the other hand, nine students commented on Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*, 5 of which have SVA errors, while 4 have none.

Table 1.2.A. Frequency Distribution of Section F Comments on Video 1

<i>Video 1(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
With SVA Errors	4	40.0
Without SVA Errors	6	60.0
	10	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table is generated, showing the frequency distribution of Section F comments in Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, based on those with SVA errors and those with none. 40% of the 10 comments commit SVA errors, while the remaining 60% have no errors. This reveals that most of the comments from Section F in Video 1 commit fewer SVA errors.

Table 1.2.B Frequency Distribution of Section F Comments on Video 2

<i>Video 2 (Qualitative Research Designs)</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
With SVA Errors	5	55.6
Without SVA Errors	4	44.4
	9	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table is generated, showing the frequency distribution of Section F comments in Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*, based on those with SVA errors and those with none. 55.6% of the nine comments commit SVA errors, while the remaining 44.4% have no errors. This reveals that most of the comments from Section F in Video 2 commit more SVA errors.

2. What is the frequency distribution of Section D students of the Ed303 course who committed SVA errors in each of the two videos in terms of:
 - i. sex;
 - ii. majorship; and
 - iii. type of previous school graduated from (either public or private school)?

Table 2.1 Sex of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in the Two Videos Selected

SECTION D (TTh 10:00-11:30 AM)	SEX		Total (out of 21 comments)
	MALE	FEMALE	
Video 1 (<i>Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs</i>)	1	8	9
Video 2 (<i>Qualitative Research Designs</i>)	2	3	5

Table 2.1 shows the classification of the number of students from Section D who committed SVA errors based on their sex. In Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, a total of 9 students committed SVA errors: 1 Male and 8 Female. On the other hand, in Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*, five students committed SVA errors: 2 Male and 3 Female.

The higher incidence of SVA errors among female students, particularly in Video 1, may reflect underlying differences in language processing and writing anxiety between genders. Research by Sugianto et al. (2023) indicates that female students tend to produce more linguistic errors in narrative writing than their male counterparts, potentially due to higher writing anxiety levels. Similarly, Hz (2024) found that female students exhibited more significant writing anxiety, which can negatively impact grammatical accuracy.

The reduced errors observed in Video 2 suggests that topic familiarity or reduced cognitive load may enhance grammatical performance. Sugianto et al. (2023) noted that when students engage with familiar or less complex topics, their writing exhibits fewer errors, likely due to increased confidence and reduced anxiety.

These findings underscore the importance of addressing writing anxiety and providing targeted grammatical instruction, particularly for female students, to improve writing

accuracy. Incorporating anxiety-reduction strategies and offering practice with diverse writing topics may help mitigate SVA errors across genders.

Table 2.1.A Sex Frequency Distribution of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 1

<i>Sex of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 1</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Male	1	11.1
Female	8	88.9
	9	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the sex frequency distribution of Section D students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*. 11.1% of the nine students with SVA errors are male, while 88.9% are female. This reveals that female students from Section D commit more SVA errors than male students in Video 1.

Table 2.1.B Sex Frequency Distribution of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2

<i>Sex of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Male	2	40.0
Female	3	60.0
	5	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the sex frequency distribution of Section D students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*. Forty percent of the five students with SVA errors are male, while 60% are female. This reveals that female students from Section D commit more SVA errors than male students in Video 2.

Table 2.2 Majorship of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in the Two Videos Selected

SECTION D (TTh 10:00-11:30 AM)	MAJORSHIP		Total (out of 21 comments)
	ENGLISH	FILIPINO	
Video 1 (Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)	2	7	9

Video 2 <i>(Qualitative Research Designs)</i>	0	5	5
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Table 2.2 shows the classification of the number of students from Section D who committed SVA errors based on their majors. In Video 1, *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, 9 students committed SVA errors: 2 from English majors and seven from Filipino majors. On the other hand, in Video 2, *Qualitative Research Designs*, none of the English majors, while 5 of the Filipino majors, committed SVA errors.

The higher incidence of SVA errors among Filipino majors than English majors may be attributed to differences in language proficiency and exposure. English majors typically receive more extensive training in English grammar and writing, which can lead to greater accuracy in subject-verb agreement. In contrast, students majoring in other disciplines may not receive the same level of grammatical instruction, potentially resulting in a higher frequency of errors. This observation aligns with findings from Hardi et al. (2022), who noted that students focusing less on English language studies tend to make more grammatical errors in their writing.

Additionally, Nurjanah (2017) found that subject-verb agreement errors are prevalent among students whose primary language of instruction is not English, further supporting the observed trend in your data.

The absence of errors among English majors in Video 2 suggests that their specialized training may contribute to better grammatical performance, even in complex topics. This is consistent with research by Hardi et al. (2022), which indicates that focused language instruction enhances grammatical accuracy.

Table 2.2.A Majorship Frequency Distribution of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 1

<i>Majorship Frequency Distribution of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 1</i>			
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>	
English	2	22.2	
Filipino	7	77.8	
	9	100.0	

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the majorship frequency distribution of Section D students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*. 22.2% of the nine students with SVA errors are English majors, while 77.8% are Filipino majors. This reveals that Filipino major students in Section D commit more SVA errors than the English major students in Video 1.

Table 2.2.B Majorship Frequency Distribution of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2

<i>Majorship Frequency Distribution of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>

English	0	0.0
Filipino	5	100.0
	5	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the majorship frequency distribution of Section D students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*. The values show that no English major students commit SVA errors in their comments on Video 2, while 5 Filipino major students do, comprising 100% of the distribution. This reveals that only the Filipino major students in Section D commit SVA errors in their comments in Video 2.

Table 2.3 Type of Previous School of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in the Two Videos Selected

SECTION D (TTh 10:00-11:30 AM)	TYPE OF PREVIOUS SCHOOL		Total
	PUBLIC	PRIVATE	
Video 1 (<i>Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs</i>)	6	3	9
Video 2 (<i>Qualitative Research Designs</i>)	2	3	5

Table 2.3 shows the classification of the number of students from Section D who committed SVA errors based on the type of school they previously attended in Senior High School (either public or private). In Video 1, *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, 9 students committed SVA errors: 6 from public schools and three from private schools. On the other hand, in Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*, 2 of the students who commit SVA errors come from a public school, while three come from private schools.

Table 2.3.A Frequency Distribution of the Type of Previous School of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 1

<i>Type of Previous School of Section D Students with SVA Errors in Video 1</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Public	6	66.7
Private	3	33.3
	9	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the frequency distribution of the type of previous school Section D students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*. 66.7% of the nine students with SVA errors come from a public school, while 33.3% come from a private school. This reveals that most of those students in Section D with SVA errors in Video 1 come from a public school.

The higher incidence of SVA errors among students from public schools may be attributed to differences in educational resources, teacher qualifications, and language instruction quality between public and private institutions. Research by **Dolba (2023)** highlights that Filipino students learning English often face challenges due to well-formed speech habits in their native language, which differ significantly from English in form,

meaning, and distribution. This discrepancy can lead to grammatical errors, including issues with subject-verb agreement. Furthermore, **Dolba (2023)** emphasizes that the deterioration in English proficiency among Filipino students directly results from the declining quality of the educational system in both private and public schools. Factors such as experienced English teachers leaving for better-paying jobs overseas have contributed to this decline, resulting in a significant portion of college graduates possessing substandard English skills.

Table 2.3.B Frequency Distribution of the Type of Previous School of Section D Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2

<i>Type of Previous School of Section D Students with SVA Errors in Video 2</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Public	2	40.0
Private	3	60.0
	5	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the frequency distribution of the type of previous school Section D students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*. Forty percent of the 10 students with SVA errors come from a public school, while 60% come from a private school. This reveals that the majority of those students in Section D with SVA errors in Video 2 come from a private school.

3. **What is the frequency distribution of Section F students of the Ed303 course who committed SVA errors in each of the two videos in terms of:**
- i. **sex; and**
 - ii. **type of previous school graduated from (either public or private school)?**

Table 3.1 Sex of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in the Two Videos Selected

SECTION F (TTh 2:30-4:00 PM)	SEX		Total (out of 21 comments)
	MALE	FEMALE	
Video 1 <i>(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>	1	3	4
Video 2 <i>(Qualitative Research Designs)</i>	1	4	5

Table 3.1 shows the classification of the number of students from Section F who committed SVA errors based on their sex. In Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, a total of 4 students committed SVA errors: 1 Male and 3 Female. On the other hand, in Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*, five students committed SVA errors: 1 Male and 4 Female.

The data indicates a higher incidence of SVA errors among female students than male students in both videos. This observation aligns with findings from Molin (2020), who noted

that female students tend to perform better academically than male students, including in areas related to subject-verb agreement.

Additionally, Kirova and Camacho (2021) found that gender agreement errors are prevalent among students whose primary language of instruction is not English, further supporting the observed trend in your data.

Table 3.1.A Sex Frequency Distribution of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 1

<i>Sex of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 1</i>		
<i>(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Male	1	25.0
Female	3	75.0
	4	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the sex frequency distribution of Section F students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*. 25% of the four students with SVA errors are male, while 75% are female. This reveals that female students from Section F commit more SVA errors than male students in Video 1.

Table 3.1.B Sex Frequency Distribution of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2

<i>Sex of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Male	1	20.0
Female	4	80.0
	5	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table is generated showing the sex frequency distribution of Section F students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*. 20% of the seven students with SVA errors are male, while 80% are female. This reveals that more female students from Section F commit SVA errors than male students in Video 2.

Table 3.2 Type of Previous School of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in the Two Videos Selected

SECTION F <i>(TTh 2:30-4:00 PM)</i>	TYPE OF PREVIOUS SCHOOL		Total
	PUBLIC	PRIVATE	
Video 1 <i>(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>	4	0	4
Video 2 <i>(Qualitative Research Designs)</i>	5	0	5

Table 3.2 shows the classification of the number of students from Section F who committed SVA errors based on the type of school they previously attended in Senior High School (either public or private). In Video 1, *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*, a total of 4 students commit SVA errors, all of whom come from a public school. On the other hand, in Video 2, *Qualitative Research Designs*, 5 students commit SVA errors, all of whom come from a public school.

The observation that only students from public schools committed SVA errors highlights a potential difference in English language instruction and exposure between public and private schools. Research by Dolba (2023) indicates that students from public schools, especially in countries with developing educational infrastructures, may not receive as much focus on grammar and language conventions as those in private schools. This could lead to a higher frequency of errors, such as SVA mistakes.

Table 3.2.A Frequency Distribution of the Type of Previous School of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in Video

<i>Type of Previous School of Section F Students with SVA Errors in Video 1</i>		
<i>(Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs)</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Public	4	100.0
Private	0	0.0
	4	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the frequency distribution of the type of previous school Section F students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 1 *Experimental Designs and Ex Post Facto Designs*. 100% of the four students with SVA errors come from a public school, while none come from a private school. This reveals that those students in Section F with SVA errors in Video 1 all come from a public school.

Table 3.2.B Frequency Distribution of the Type of Previous School of Section F Students with SVA Errors Found in Video 2

<i>Type of Previous School of Section F Students with SVA Errors in Video 2</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Public	5	100.0
Private	0	0.0
	5	100.0

Using MegaStat, the above table shows the frequency distribution of the type of previous school Section F students with SVA errors in their comments on Video 2 *Qualitative Research Designs*. 100% of the five students with SVA errors come from a

public school, while none from a private school. This reveals that those students in Section F with SVA errors in Video 2 all come from a public school.

4. What are the reasons why students commit these SVA errors?

Table 4.1 Tally of Students' Responses

REASONS	FREQUENCY
<i>Lack of foundational knowledge about SVA rules</i>	6
<i>First language preference</i>	2
<i>Absence of comprehensive knowledge on SVA</i>	5
<i>Confusion about the SVA rules</i>	6
<i>Failure to review and proofread the written outputs because of time constraints</i>	5

Total: 24

Table 4.1 shows the tally of the 24 students' responses on the reasons why they commit SVA errors: 6 students responded that they commit SVA errors because of the lack of foundational knowledge about it; 2 students said it is because of the first language preference; 5 students noted that it is due to absence of comprehensive knowledge on SVA; 6 students responded that it is because of the confusion about the SVA rules, and five students said that it is due to failure to review and proofread the written outputs because of time constraints.

These findings align with research indicating that students often struggle with SVA due to various factors. For instance, Putri et al. (2023) identified that students' difficulties in using SVA stemmed from interlingual errors (2%) and intralingual and developmental errors (98%). Furthermore, Hardi et al. (2022) emphasized that students' lack of understanding of SVA rules and their first language interference contribute significantly to these errors.

During the interview, the researchers noted that one of the 24 responses was in the respondent's *vernacular—Cebuano*. The researchers transcribed this response and translated it into English. Additionally, this response belongs to the category of "confusion about the SVA rules."

Transcript/translation of the lone vernacular response:

“maong masayup ky usahay malibog mo [ko] ug unsa jud ang correct na grammar ana na words ky [kay] feel nako mura siyag correct kay pag akong basahon, okay ra man siya paminawun.”

Translation:

I commit errors because I get confused with the correct grammatical rules, as when I read it [referring to the written reflective output], it sounded okay to me.

Table 4.2 Frequency Distribution of the Reasons Why Students Commit SVA Errors

<i>Reasons Why Students Commit SVA Errors</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Lack of foundational knowledge of SVA rules	6	25.0
First language preference	2	8.3
Absence of comprehensive knowledge on SVA	5	20.8
Confusion about the SVA rules	6	25.0
Failure to review and proofread the written outputs because of time constraints	5	20.8
	24	100.0

Table 4.2 shows the frequency distribution of why students commit SVA errors. Out of the 24 responses, 25% is due to lack of foundational knowledge on SVA rules, 8.3% is due to first language preference, 20.8% is due to absence of comprehensive knowledge on SVA, 25% is due to confusion about the SVA rules, and 20.8 percent is due to failure to review and proofread the written outputs because of time constraints.

5. What course of action can be taken based on the findings?

- 5.1. The findings indicate that many comments contain SVA errors, particularly in Video 1, with improvements observed in Video 2. To address this, a comparative analysis of the activities associated with both videos can be conducted to determine factors contributing to the reduced number of errors in Video 2. Specific examples from students' comments should be used during class discussions to highlight correct and incorrect SVA usage, providing clarity and reinforcement. Additionally, reflective activities can be introduced where students review their comments, identify SVA errors, and propose corrections to foster self-awareness and strengthen their understanding.
- 5.2. For Section D, the findings reveal that female students, Filipino majors, and graduates from public schools exhibit higher rates of SVA errors. To address these patterns, small-group sessions can be organized based on sex, majorship, or educational background to provide targeted support that caters to specific challenges. Supplemental materials focusing on grammatical rules can be developed for Filipino majors, as they exhibit more frequent errors than English majors. Activities tailored to public school graduates should bridge foundational grammar gaps. Furthermore, inclusive discussions addressing how educational backgrounds influence SVA understanding can help create awareness and provide tailored resources to enhance learning outcomes.
- 5.3. For Section F, the data indicate that female students and graduates from public schools have higher rates of SVA errors. To address these issues, gender-sensitive grammar workshops can be organized to explore why female students tend to commit more SVA errors and to provide strategies to overcome these challenges. Targeted grammar practice sessions for public school graduates can focus on the typical patterns of errors identified in the data. Additionally, collaborative exercises that pair students from diverse educational backgrounds can be implemented to foster peer learning to allow students to share insights and improve collectively.
- 5.4. The findings reveal that students commit SVA errors due to a lack of foundational knowledge, first-language interference, confusion about rules, insufficient comprehensive understanding, and failure to proofread due to time constraints. To address these issues, foundational gaps can be addressed by integrating SVA-

focused lessons into the curriculum with activities designed to increase complexity gradually. Activities highlighting the contrasts between students' first language and English should also be developed, emphasizing areas prone to SVA errors. Simplified SVA rule guides and visual aids can be provided for quick reference during writing tasks, while proofreading checklists and time management strategies can encourage students to identify and correct errors effectively. Quizzes and interactive games can further reinforce the understanding of SVA rules engagingly.

A *Raising Awareness Session* will be conducted for students from Sections D and F of Ed303 as part of the intervention. This session will present the findings, highlight common errors, and introduce a program of activities to help students master SVA rules. The session will also encourage reflection on errors overlooked in their comments on Dr. Craig N. Refugio's YouTube videos. Moreover, *collaboration with the English Aficionados Community (EAC)*, the university's English club, will involve developing short-term and long-term action plans. The short-term plan includes 3–4 tutorial or training sessions focusing on SVA rules. For the long term, the researchers will seek consent from EAC advisers, propose free programs and activities, and offer access to tools like Grammarly to enhance students' grammatical knowledge. These strategies aim to provide comprehensive support to improve students' understanding and application of SVA.

Stage 3: Developing Stage

Step 7: Develop an action plan

I. Conclusion:

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are made:

- I.1. The analysis of the comments of the combined population of Ed303 Sections D and F on the two selected videos indicates that most students from both sections committed Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) errors, highlighting a prevalent challenge in their written responses.
- I.2. The findings reveal notable patterns in the frequency distribution of SVA errors among Section D students of the Ed303 course. Regarding sex, more errors are committed by female students than by male students. Regarding majors, Filipino majors account for a significantly higher proportion of SVA errors than English majors. Lastly, regarding the type of school graduated from, students from public schools contribute to a majority of the SVA errors compared to students from private schools.
- I.3. The findings indicate clear trends in the frequency distribution of SVA errors among Section F students of the Ed303 course. In terms of sex, a higher percentage of SVA errors are committed by female students compared to male students. Regarding the type of school they graduated from, all students who committed SVA errors are from public schools, with no errors recorded from private school graduates.
- I.4. When it comes to the perceived reasons why SVA errors are frequently committed, it was revealed that the primary reasons why students commit SVA errors are lack of foundational knowledge and confusion about the SVA rules. The secondary reasons are the absence of comprehensive knowledge of SVA and the failure to review and proofread the written outputs because of time constraints. Finally, the last reason students commit SVA errors is their preference for their first language over their second language.

- I.5. Addressing the students' recurrent SVA errors requires integrating SVA-focused lessons, providing practical tools like guides and proofreading strategies, and fostering engagement through awareness sessions and collaborations with the English Aficionados Community. These combined efforts aim to enhance students' understanding and effective application of SVA rules.

II. Recommended Action

The course of action stated above was congested into two major steps:

II.1. Raising Awareness Session Together with the Students from Sections D and F of Ed303

The researchers enact strategies to share and communicate the results to the people involved. In this activity, the summary, approaches, and reflection of the results are presented to them to inform them of the errors that they may have overlooked while answering the reflection activity on Dr. Craig N. Refugio's YouTube channel. A program of activities is introduced to them where they can hone and better master their knowledge of SVA rules.

II.2. Collaboration with the English Aficionados Community, an English Club

Following the review of published literature and discussions of the researchers with the officials of the English Aficionados Community (EAC), the researchers decided to develop a short-term and long-term action plan. The researchers propose to conduct 3-4 sessions (short term) of tutorial or training about the rules of SVA.

On the other hand, the long-term action plan involves informed consent and permission from the adviser and officers of the English Aficionados Community (EAC). The researchers propose free programs or activities for students to the EAC President and Advisers. They also offer access to Grammarly software and other tools that can help them improve their grammatical knowledge of the second language.

III. Person Involved

These recommended actions involve the researchers themselves, the research subjects who are in the persons of the Sections D and F students of Ed303 Methods of Research in Education A.Y. 2022-2023, the English Aficionados Community officers/advisers, and a few English major teachers in the university.

IV. Data Collector

The data collectors are the researchers themselves, as they provide supplementary programs intended to develop SVA knowledge among the identified college students.

V. Person/s to Monitor and Evaluate

The researchers themselves monitor and evaluate the program of activities. Their research adviser may intervene and provide suggestions for improving the recommended actions.

VI. Target Time of Accomplishment

The target time for this program of activities is before the end of the second semester of the academic year 2022-2023.

VII. Resources Needed

As the researchers foresaw, a multimedia classroom, laptop, projector/Smart TV, pieces of paper, and pens are the only resources needed, as the recommended actions are more like lectures in which participants receive input.

VIII. Budget Allocation

The accessibility and availability of the aforementioned devices/resources can significantly decrease or even eliminate financial concerns.

Stage 4: Reflecting Stage

Step 8: Sharing and communicating results

The researchers shared the results shown in the previous stage with the following subjects, who were expected to benefit from this study's findings.

1. **The students.** The students are expected to learn more effectively and become more adept at using proper grammar and crafting correct English texts. They are expected to write more proficiently and with fewer SVA errors.
2. **The teacher.** English teachers can improve the teaching-learning process by using specific techniques in the language teaching methodology.
3. **The CTED English Department.** The study's findings can expand teaching methods and techniques appropriate for the current curricula.
4. **The school.** The findings of this study can be shared with other educators to help them use techniques more clearly and raise the standard of writing instruction using SVA rules in classrooms.

Step 9: Reflecting on the process

The researchers reflected on the process of their study and identified several insights. In hindsight, they noted that including other grammatical errors beyond SVA could have enriched the findings. Expanding the scope of participants to include all commenters on the selected YouTube videos would have provided a broader dataset. They also recognized the potential value of incorporating mobile learning applications, such as the one developed by Miranda et al. (2021), to make interventions more engaging.

Despite differences in sex, majorship, or school background, the study emphasized that achieving proficiency in SVA relies on individual effort and foundational knowledge. This lack of foundational knowledge, potentially stemming from insufficient early education or ineffective teaching methods, emerged as the primary reason for persistent SVA errors at the tertiary level. Ultimately, the research highlights the prevalence of SVA errors among Ed303 students at NORSU, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to address this challenge.

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